

Biological and Toxicological Effects of Aqueous Extract of *Strychnos Spinosa* (spiny monkey orange) Leaf on “Heteroclarias”

*Akin-Obasola, B.J.¹, Muhammed E.A.² and Aiyelari, T.A.³

^{1, 2, 3}Department of Fisheries and Aquaculture Management, Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti, Nigeria.

¹Corresponding author: bola.akinobasola@eksu.edu.ng +2348033100012

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Abstract

The study evaluated the toxicological and biological effects of *Strychnos spinosa* (Spiny Monkey Orange) leaf extract on “Heteroclarias”. Fish farmers rely on conventional medications to deworm fish, which is costly and have side effects that takes longer time to dissipate from fish system hence the use of *Strychnos spinosa* as a cheaper and readily available alternative. The study aimed to determine the acute toxicity, behavioural responses, and histopathological effects of *Strychnos spinosa* leaf extract on “Heteroclarias” under controlled conditions. A 96-hour static bioassay was conducted using “Heteroclarias” fingerlings exposed to varying concentrations (0, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35 g/15L in range finding test and 0, 6, 8, 10 and 12 g/15L in definitive test) of *Strychnos spinosa* extract. Fish were monitored for mortality rates, behavioural changes, and histopathological alterations. Water quality parameters; pH, dissolved oxygen, and temperature, were also analysed. The lethal median concentration (LC₅₀) was determined graphically to be 10.5g/15L. Histopathological examination of vital organs, including the skin and liver, demonstrated severe structural damages at higher concentrations. The study concludes that *Strychnos spinosa* leaf extract exerts significant toxic effects on “Heteroclarias” at higher concentrations above the LC₅₀.

Keywords: Acute, toxicity, histopathology, organs, *Strychnos spinosa*

INTRODUCTION

Aquaculture has emerged as a vital food source that meets the growing global demand for animal protein and this supports the livelihoods of millions worldwide, contributing significantly to food security and economic growth (Dauda and Adelaja, 2018). Among the fish species cultivated for aquaculture, “Heteroclarias” holds a prominent position, primarily due to its high resilience, faster growth rates, improved feed conversion ratios and favorable growth traits. “Heteroclarias” is a hybrid of the African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) and the vundu catfish (*Heterobranchus longifilis*), blending the rapid growth of *Clarias* with the hardiness of *Heterobranchus*. Despite these advantages, the health and productivity of “Heteroclarias” can be significantly impacted by exposure to environmental pollutants and the introduction of toxic substances into aquatic habitat (Fafioye, 2011).

The *Strychnos* genus, belonging to the family Loganiaceae, consists of over 190 species, most of which are known for their medicinal and toxic properties. *Strychnos spinosa* is a tropical African species commonly found in savannah and semi-arid regions. It is believed to contain various bioactive compounds including alkaloids, glycosides, and tannins that could potentially exert toxic effects on living organisms at higher concentrations (Ogunwenmo and Ekundayo, 2005).

Plate 1: *Strychnos spinosa* (Jenway and Tiwari, 1971)

The sustainability and productivity of aquaculture systems are vulnerable to contamination from plants when used to manage various daily concerns such as deworming in fish farming. However, the toxicological effects of its bioactive compounds, particularly alkaloids and tannins, raise concerns about its potential impact on aquatic organisms (Adeyemi *et al*, 2014).

Fish farmers rely on conventional medications to deworm fish, which is costly and have side effects that takes longer time to dissipate from fish system. Therefore, the use of medicinal plants like *Strychnos spinosa* is suggested as an alternatives in deworming fish which serves the same purpose as conventional medicines but offers a higher therapeutic effect when the correct dose is given hence the need for comprehensive research on its toxicological studies to mitigate the risks posed by the plant (Adeyemi *et al*, 2014). This gap in knowledge could potentially jeopardize the health of farmed fish populations, the livelihoods of fish farmers and food security in affected regions (Zornu, 2023).

The specific objectives of this study are to carry out range finding test, LC₅₀ (lethal median concentration), assess the biological responses and the histopathology of vital organs (skin and liver) of “Heteroclaris” exposed to different levels of *Strychnos spinosa* leaf.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A 96-hour static bioassay was conducted using fingerlings of “Heteroclaris” with a mean weight of $4.69 \pm 0.10\text{g}$ as test organisms. A total of 360 apparently healthy “Heteroclaris” fingerlings were obtained from a reputable fish farm in Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria. The fish were held in plastic tanks with dimensions of 45 cm x 30 cm x 40 cm for acclimation. They were allowed to acclimatize for three (3) days in the wet lab. Before the experiment commencement, the fish were fed to satiation with a commercial diet of 35% crude protein. *Strychnos spinosa* was collected from Ado/Ikere Ekiti environment, milled, and kept in an airtight container until it was needed.

Range finding test:

Range-finding test was conducted under standard bioassay procedures. The test was conducted using twenty-one (21) transparent rectangular plastic tanks of 25-litre capacity, each filled with 15 liters of water prior to the introduction of milled *Strychnos spinosa* leaf. Ten (10) fingerlings of “Heteroclaris” per tank were used for the test and each treatment was in triplicates. Feeding was discontinued a day before the experiment and the test monitored for 24 hours at 3-hour interval and mortality recorded.

Definitive test:

A total of 150 “Heteroclaris” fingerlings were used for the five treatments used. Experimental designs used in range finding test was repeated.

Determination of behavioral responses of fish:

The reactions observed included erratic swimming patterns, loss of reflex, discoloration, behavioral changes, hyperventilation, and molting. The tests were done using Histology Laboratory Manual, 2011-2012 methods.

Determination of physicochemical parameters of the water:

The temperature, dissolved oxygen concentration, and pH was monitored. The temperature was measured with a clinical thermometer, dissolved oxygen with dissolved oxygen meter and the pH with pH meter. These parameters were determined every 24 hours using standard methods (Jenway 1971).

Histopathology:

The skin and liver were fixed for 24 hours in formal-saline solution made of equal volumes of 10% formalin and 0.9% sodium chloride solution. Histological sections of 5µm thickness was prepared following standard procedures (Histology Laboratory Manual, 2011-2012). Photomicrographs were taken with Leitz (Ortholux) microscope and camera.

Statistical and graphical Analysis:

The LC₅₀ values were determined graphically. Other data on physicochemical parameters were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS software version 22 (SPSS Inc., Chicago). Duncan's multiple range test was used for post-hoc analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Behavioral Changes in Acute toxicity test:

The higher the concentration of *Strynos spinosa*, the more the behavioral changes experienced by the fish. Fish showed loss of reflex, Erratic Swimming pattern, discoloration, hyperventilation and mortality. This corroborate Adebayo *et al.*, (2013) when *Clarias anguillaris* was introduced to a sub-lethal concentration of diazinon and increased physical activity, convulsion, excess secretions of liver tissues, erratic swimming, and sudden quick movement was recorded.

The range finding test:

This was done using six (6) treatments; 0g/15L, 10g/15 L, 15g/15L, 20g/15L, 25g/15L and 30g/15L respectively. Table 1 shows that, mortality increased as the concentration and number of hours increased. High mortality (100 %) was recorded at concentration 30g/15L while after 24 hours, concentration 25g/15L had 100% mortality. These range of mortality informed the concentrations used in definitive test.

Table 1: Range finding test: Percentage mortality of “Heteroclarias” exposed to different levels of *Strychnos spinosa* leaf

Concentrations	Time (hours)					Total mortality
	3hrs	6hrs	9hrs	12hrs	24 hrs	
0g/15 Liters	0	0	0	0	0	0
10g/15litres	10	30	10	0	10	60
15g/15Litres	20	20	20	10	10	80
20g/15litres	0	100	0	0	0	100

25g/15litres	100	0	0	0	0	100
30g/15litres	100	0	0	0	0	100
35g/15litres	100	0	0	0	0	100

The definitive test (Acute toxicity test):

Five (5) treatments (0, 6, 8, 10 and 12g/15 L) was used as shown in Table 2, the results revealed that as the concentration of *Strychnos spinosa* increases, the percentage mortality increased within the first 24 hours. In this test, total mortality was recorded in the concentrations 20, 25, 30, and 35 g/15L agreeing with Shastry and Sharma, (1979) who recorded total mortality within 24 hours when copper concentrations of 2.61 and 5.60 mg/l were used on juvenile red drum, *Sciaenops ocellatus* and 97% mortality within 24 hours when 1.36 mg/l of copper was used.

Table 2: Definitive test (Acute toxicity test): % Mortality of “Heteroclaris” exposed to different levels of *Strychnos spinosa* leaf within 96 hours Bioassay.

Concentrations	Time (hours)				Total mortality
	24hrs	48hrs	72hrs	96hrs	
0 g/15 Liters	0	0	0	0	0
6 g/15 Liters	10	20	0	0	30
8 g/15 Liters	20	20	20	0	60
10g/15 Liters	10	20	30	10	70
12g/15 Liters	20	20	20	20	80

Water quality analysis: Water analysis (apart from the control experiment) showed that there were little differences in temperature (25°C - 26°C), pH (7-8) and dissolved oxygen (5mg/L – 6 mg/L) values of the water used throughout the experiment. Dissolved oxygen reduced as the concentration of toxicant increased; this report is similar to Duffus, (1980) where environmental toxicology was studied.

Median lethal concentration (LC₅₀):

The 96 hours LC₅₀ was recorded graphically at 10.5g/15 L concentration as shown in Figure 1.

Graph 1: The LC₅₀ (Median lethal concentration) of *Strynos innocua*

Figure 1: Median lethal concentration (LC₅₀) = 10.5g/15L

Histopathological findings

The histopathological findings on the skin as well as the liver of “Heteroclaris” exposed to different concentrations (0, 6, 8, 10 and 12 g/15L of water) of *Strynos spinosa* are as shown in Plates 1 and 2.

Skin: The skin at 0g/15L of “Heteroclaris” appeared normal while at a lower concentration (10g/15L), it was un-deformed and the peeling of the skin was not pronounced. The colour of the fish skin changed and took after the colour (milk brown) of the tested material (Plates b, c, d and e) in all the concentrations except the control experiment. There was deformation in the skin of “Heteroclaris” exposed to different levels, this agrees with Akin-Obasola, (2019) who recorded deformation in the epidermal cells in the skin of “Heteroclaris” exposed to higher concentrations of petrol and engine oil mixture tested for acute and sub-lethal effects.

Histopathological changes in the skin of “Heteroclaris” (Magnification = X100)

Plate 1a: Section at 0g/15

Plate 1b: Section at 6g/15L

Plate 1c: Section at 8g/15L

Plate 1d: Section at 10g/15L

Plate 1e: Section at 12g/15L

Plates 1a-e: Sections of Skin in “heteroclaris” exposed to *Strynos spinosa* Leaf (Mag = 100)

Liver: The liver tissues of “Heteroclaris” exposed to 0g/15L of water showed normal hepatocellular architecture. The higher concentration of *Strynos spinosa* Leaf showed moderate to severe cytoplasmic vacuolation and peripherally placed nuclei.

Plate 2a: Section at 0g/15L

Plate 2b: Section at 6g/15L

Plate 2c: Section at 8g/15L

Plate 2d: Section at 10g/15L

Plate 2e: Section at 12g/15L

Plates 1a-e: Sections of liver in “heteroclaris” exposed to *Strynos spinosa* Leaf (Mag = X100)

“Heteroclaris” exposed to different levels of *Strynos spinosa* had the presence of the toxicant in the skin and liver. This suggests that these organs could be useful as a marker for the presence of toxicants in the aquatic environment, this corroborates Ray *et al*, (1999) who recorded a high concentration of mercuric in the liver and other organs of “Heteroclaris” when the concentration of mercuric in the tissues increased.

The accumulation of *Strynos spinosa* in fish tissue increased with increasing toxicant concentration in water, this result agreed with Olaifa *et al*, (2003).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The LC₅₀ value determined in this study was 10.5g/15L and this concentration level provides useful information for the management and safety of using *Strynos spinosa* for deworming in fish farming practice, helping to ensure that *Strynos spinosa* is used in a way that minimizes harmful effects on fish health.

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